

Academic Stress, Adjustment Styles, and Study Habits of Nursing Students at Isabela State University – Echague Campus: A Correlational Studies

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Abstract:- The following paper offers a thorough analysis of the connections among student study habits, adjustment styles, and academic stress. Students of all academic levels frequently experience academic stress, resulting in adverse impacts on both their well-being and academic achievements. On the other hand, adjustment styles refer to the coping mechanisms and emotional reactions used by students to handle the difficulties and demands of the academic environment. The methods and behaviors that students use in their learning and studying activities are referred to as study habits. The aim of this study is to explore how students cope with academic stress, adapt to various adjustment styles, and engage in study habits. Quantitative research is used in this topic: “Academic Stress, Adjustment Style, and Study Habits of Nursing Students at Isabela State University Echague campus: a correlational study”. The respondents of this study contain 406 people following 4-year level and 10 Sections. A Likert scale Appendix A is used which ranges from Extremely Stress to No stress and for the Appendix B is used which ranges to Always to Never and for Appendix C is used which ranges from Rarely to review producer can hear an all-encompassing individual Stressors. A written questionnaire consisting of 76 statements was distributed to the respondents to gather data needed for this study. The findings of this study with regards Academic Stressor is Moderate Stress and for Adjustment Styles is Sometimes moreover Study Habits shows Sometimes, respectively. For future researchers who are conducting research that might

tackle Academic Stress, Adjustment Style and Study Habits, this study is highly recommended for reference.

Keywords:- Academic Stress; Adjustment Style; Study Habits.

I. INTRODUCTION

Education plays a vital role in an individual's life, serving as a pivotal juncture in their academic journey. During this phase, a student's performance significantly influences the trajectory of their education, ultimately shaping their professional future. Experiencing excessive academic stress at this juncture can lead to enduring and far-reaching negative consequences. According to Bennion et al. (2018) argue that our notion of an ideal school is centered on the shared aim of readying young individuals for adulthood. Beyond equipping students for business and career challenges, this preparation extends to instilling ethical and attitudinal values reflective of the times. While schools aim to teach and replicate real-world situations, they inadvertently introduce an additional authentic experience: student stress. The heightened stress levels primarily stem from the numerous adjustments demanded by college life.

College is a third level of education wherein it will be the steppingstone to choosing a career in order to enhance the student's knowledge and skills in a particular program that they want to pursue in the future. However, students cannot focus on their goal because there are hindrances to

their learning. As reported by the American College Health Association (2015), extensive research highlights stress as a predominant academic obstacle affecting students in numerous US colleges and universities. The study indicates that 40% of American students admit to inadequate rest on five out of seven days weekly. Moreover, a quarter of American college students attribute sleep deprivation to negative academic consequences, such as lower grades, missed deadlines, and discontinuation of studies. The survey also reveals varied stress levels, with 45% reporting "more than average stress," 33% indicating "moderate stress," and 12.7% describing it as "tremendous stress." Notably, only 9% reported feeling "no stress" or "less stressful than average." Similarly, in the United Kingdom, 8 out of 10 university students report experiencing stress and/or anxiety, with 45% expressing stress related to their courses—exceeding the proportion of students who find enjoyment in their academic pursuits (41%).

Filipino students are experiencing academic stress due to the transition from online learning to face-to-face classes, and they must adjust and change their lifestyles in order to cope. There is a huge difference in lifestyle between online learning and face-to-face classes. As outlined by Bernal, Caguimbal, et al. (2017), students predominantly encounter stress related to their lifestyle and the perception of academic stress, which, in turn, impacts their academic performance. The research suggests that in the context of online classes, utilizing technology eases class preparation. However, in face-to-face classes, students may contend with the need to physically attend school and wake up early for the initial subject. Additionally, stressors include the volume of work assigned by professors. A subsequent study by Dy, Ria, et al. (2015) emphasizes that studies and workload emerge as significant stress factors for students. This encompasses factors like the courses selected, assignments, requirements, exams, other responsibilities, and the perceived significance of assignments, collectively influencing how students perceive and navigate their workload throughout a semester.

Stress is part of the life of students, and it is a factor in motivating them to study in order to keep up with the lessons and activities. College is not easy, and there is no effortless program in college; students have to deal with this to develop their skills. The study wanted to enhance the learning of the students and the teaching engagement of the respondents. Gaining insights into the underlying causes of stress will enable the school to create targeted counseling modules and intervention strategies, with the goal of aiding students in managing and reducing stress.

➤ Purpose

The purpose of the study is to determine the level of stress among the nursing students who officially enrolled during the first semester. The study seeks to know the experiences, adjustment to another environment, and

changes in study habits of the nursing students in transition from online classes to face-to-face learning.

II. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

A descriptive correlational study design was used by the researchers. Data are gathered using the descriptive correlational study design to ascertain whether there is a relationship between two or more variables. The study was conducted at Isabela State University Echague Campus College of Nursing. The respondents of the study are nursing students who are currently enrolled during the 1st semester S.Y. 2022 – 2023 with a total population of 564 number students and a sample size of 406 students were determined using the raosoft computation and was selected through proportional stratified sampling method. The researchers used an academic stress scale (Appendix A), Adjustment Styles Inventory (Appendix B), Study Habits Styles Inventory (Appendix C) based on the study of Zunaira Shafiq Zunaira titled "Appendices Appendix- A Academic Stress Scale". The Academic Stress Scale questionnaire is an examination created to assess academic stress to nursing students and composed of 5-point Likert scale (no stress, slight stress, moderate stress, high stress and extreme stress). The Adjustment Styles Inventory questionnaire serves as a tool for evaluating the adjustment styles of nursing students, employing a 5-point Likert scale (never, very rarely, sometimes, very often and always). The Study Habits Inventory questionnaire is utilized as a tool for gauging the study habits of nursing students, employing a 3-point Likert scale (rarely, sometimes and often). The survey was employed to assess the level of academic stress, the degree of adjustment styles, and the level of study habits. Researchers requested permission to conduct a study at the College of Nursing, which was then approved by the Dean. Participants provided informed consent, ensuring their willingness to answer survey questionnaires and confidentiality. Data was collected and organized using survey questionnaires, and the results were analyzed and interpreted. The study used statistical analysis to analyze and interpret data on nursing students' academic stress, adjustment styles, and study habits. Sociodemographic profiles were illustrated using frequency counts and percentages, while the weighted mean was employed to identify factors influencing this stress. The comparison of variables was conducted through a t-test, and significant differences were analyzed using ANOVA. The Pearson-R Test was used to measure linear correlations between academic stress, adjustment style, study habits, and adjustment style. Likert scales were used to assess levels of stress, adjustment style, and study habits. The study prioritizes ethical concerns by creating informed consent, ensuring participant anonymity, respect, and confidentiality. Participants can opt out of the study without compulsion or force, and the research will not cause harm. The researchers are open to suggestions and new ideas.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This chapter presents the outcomes of the data analysis conducted as part of the study. The researchers collected data using a distributed questionnaire in addressing the research questions.

Table 1 Profile of the Respondents

Age	Frequency	Percentage
18-20	265	65.27
21-23	141	34.73
24-27	0	0.00
Above 28	0	0.00
Total	406	100.00
Sex	Frequency	Percentage
Male	137	33.74
Female	269	66.26
Total	406	100.00
Religion	Frequency	Percent
Roman Catholic	249	61.3
Iglesia Ni Cristo	63	15.5
United Methodist Church	43	10.6
Born Again	51	12.6
Total	406	100.0
Family Monthly Income	Frequency	Percent
Below 10,957	113	27.8
10,958-21,914	186	45.8
21,915-43,828	91	22.4
43, 829-76,669	16	3.9
Total	406	100.0

The table displays the distribution of respondents based on their demographic profile, showcasing frequencies and percentages. Among the 406 respondents included in the study, the tabulated data indicates that a predominant demographic comprises individuals aged 18 to 20 years, constituting a frequency of 265 (65.27%), while those within the age range of 21 to 23 years account for 141 (34.73%). The gender distribution highlights a majority of female respondents, totaling 269 (66.26%), with male respondents comprising 137 (33.74%).

In consideration of religious affiliation among the participants, the majority adhere to Roman Catholicism, accounting for a frequency of 249 (61.3%). Other religious affiliations include Iglesia ni Cristo, with a frequency of 63 (15.5%), United Methodist Church, with a frequency of 43 (10.6%), and Born Again, with a frequency of 51 (12.6%).

In terms of Family Monthly income, most of them are under 10,958–21,914, with a frequency of 186 (45.8%), Below 10,957 with a frequency of 113 (27.8%), 21,915–43,828 with a frequency of 91 (22.4%), and 43,829–76,669 with a frequency of 16 (3.9%).

Table 2 The level of Academic Stress among Respondents

Academic Stress Scale	Mean	Descriptive Interpretation
Instructors place excessive additional requirements on students.	3.09	Moderate Stress
Lack of enthusiasm for certain subjects.	2.98	Moderate Stress
Difficulty maintaining focus during study sessions.	3.24	Moderate Stress
Struggles with recalling information studied.	3.40	Moderate Stress
Anxiety regarding the upcoming examinations.	3.46	High Stress
Absence of self-assurance.	3.12	Moderate Stress
Our ideas are not heard by the teachers.	2.74	Moderate Stress
Disagreements with friends or college authorities.	2.54	Slight Stress
Educators administer a greater number of disciplinary measures within the classroom.	3.01	Moderate Stress
Concerns about the exam outcomes.	3.52	High Stress
Reluctant to seek a comprehensive clarification from the teacher.	3.13	Moderate Stress
Prejudiced behavior exhibited by the teacher.	2.94	Moderate Stress
Lack of understanding on how to ready oneself for examinations.	3.12	Moderate Stress
Deficiency in assertiveness (confidence) within the class.	3.13	Moderate Stress
Absence of chances to meet with teachers.	2.85	Moderate Stress
The teacher reflects socio-economic status in their approach to students.	2.69	Moderate Stress

The examination papers are challenging and inadequately assessed.	3.00	Moderate Stress
Inability to finish the assignment within the specified timeframe.	3.08	Moderate Stress
Absence of communication between educators and students.	3.16	Moderate Stress
Teaching style by the instructor is monotonous, dull, or tedious.	2.97	Moderate Stress
Inadequate class discussions.	2.97	Moderate Stress
Absence of mutual assistance among classmates.	2.77	Moderate Stress
Inability to speak a language fluently other than one's mother tongue.	2.95	Moderate Stress
Challenges in delivering speeches in public.	3.25	Moderate Stress
The teacher speaks quickly and does not write clearly on the blackboard.	2.91	Moderate Stress
Educators showing a lack of interest in their students.	2.77	Moderate Stress
Grand Mean	3.03	Moderate Stress

The table indicated that on the Academic Stress Scale, concern about examinations exhibited a mean score of 3.46, categorically described as elevated stress levels among nursing students. Worry about results after examinations

revealed a mean score of 3.52 which is verbally described as high stress towards academics. Among the nursing students Overall, the grand mean revealed a mean score of 4.03 which is verbally described as moderate stress.

Table 3 The Level of Adjustment Style among Respondents

Adjustments Styles Inventory	Mean	Descriptive Interpretation
Maintaining optimism for improvement.	3.64	Very Often
Strive to retain a degree of control over the situation.	3.55	Very Often
Gather additional information about the situation so that you can manage it more effectively.	3.53	Very Often
Consider various approaches to address the situation.	3.77	Very Often
Examine the issue from an objective standpoint.	3.41	Very Often
Consume food, smoke, or chew gum.	2.73	Sometimes
Experiment with various problem-solving approaches to determine the most effective one.	3.56	Very Often
Utilize previous experiences to navigate the situation.	3.60	Very Often
Seek to derive meaning from the circumstance.	3.82	Very Often
Engage in prayer and place trust in God.	3.99	Very Often
Became anxious or felt nervous.	3.63	Very Often
Experience concern or anxiety.	3.66	Very Often
Deconstruct the problem into smaller components.	3.43	Very Often
Turn to family or friends for support or solace.	3.32	Very Often
Establish specific goals to aid in problem-solving.	3.54	Very Often
Acknowledge and embrace the situation as it currently exists.	3.50	Very Often
Desire solitude or to be by oneself.	3.46	Very Often
Find humor in the situation, considering that circumstances could be more challenging.	3.29	Sometimes
Attempt to dismiss the problem from your thoughts.	3.28	Sometimes
Engage in daydreaming or fantasizing.	3.21	Sometimes
Prepare yourself for the possibility of the worst outcome.	3.45	Very Often
Discuss the problem with someone who has experienced a similar situation.	3.21	Sometimes
Proactively seek to alter the situation.	3.18	Sometimes
Express anger, use profanity.	2.95	Sometimes
Experience sadness, become depressed.	3.19	Sometimes
Opt to sleep, anticipating a better perspective in the morning.	3.42	Very Often
Adopt a nonchalant attitude, assuming everything will likely resolve itself.	3.15	Sometimes
Retreat from the situation.	2.87	Sometimes
Alleviate tension through physical activity.	2.99	Sometimes
Accept the next best alternative.	3.36	Sometimes
Grand Mean	3.39	Sometimes

The table showed that respondents adopt through adjustment strategies in academic settings sometimes and very often. Overall, the grand mean revealed a score of 3.39 and verbally described as sometimes.

Table 4 The Study Habits among Respondents

Study Habits Inventory	Mean	Descriptive Interpretation
The material needs to be reviewed multiple times as the content does not hold much significance during the initial reading.	2.24	Sometimes
Struggling to discern the essential points in the material read or studied, often results in noting down information that later appears inconsequential.	2.15	Sometimes
Reviewing the studied material includes reciting it while going over any points that appear uncertain.	2.31	Sometimes
The act of articulating words to oneself takes place during the process of reading.	2.34	Often
Critical points in the lecture are overlooked when transcribing notes from preceding content.	2.17	Sometimes
Maintaining concentration on my studies proves to be challenging, and upon completion, recalling the content I have read becomes a struggle.	2.09	Sometimes
Engaging in study often leads to a tendency for daydreaming.	2.04	Sometimes
It takes some time to get settled and 'warmed up' for the study task.	2.18	Sometimes
Delaying the commencement of a task until 'the mood strikes' or 'an inspection' occurs can result in time wastage.	2.11	Sometimes
The study sessions are frequently insufficient for me to reach a state of focus and concentration.	2.15	Sometimes
The allocation of time is disrupted in an unwise manner, with an overemphasis on specific activities and inadequate attention directed towards others.	2.09	Sometimes
External factors like phone calls, visitors, and distracting noises disrupt study sessions.	2.10	Sometimes
Completing work by a specified deadline is challenging under pressure, resulting in unfinished, subpar, or delayed tasks.	2.00	Sometimes
Studying is done in a group rather than individually.	1.93	Sometimes
Engaging in leisure, playful wordplay, or casual conversations disrupts the studying process.	1.91	Sometimes
Excessive time spent on activities like reading fiction, going to cinemas, etc., negatively impacts college work.	1.81	Sometimes
An excessive social life disrupts academic success, including participation in dances, dates, and trips.	1.91	Sometimes
Feeling agitated and nervous during exams, there is a tendency to become overwhelmed, making it challenging to perform at one's best and effectively communicate one's knowledge.	2.07	Sometimes
Mentally strategizing the response to a subjective or essay-type examination question precedes the commencement of writing.	2.18	Sometimes
Completion of examination papers and submission occurs before the designated time elapses.	2.19	Sometimes
Attempting to grasp each point as it is encountered, rather than moving forward and subsequently revisiting uncertain points.	2.08	Sometimes
Efforts are made to summarize, classify, and systematize the acquired facts, connecting them with previously learned material and facts.	2.17	Sometimes
Attempting to engage in 'over-learning,' extending the effort beyond the immediate point of memory or recall.	2.03	Sometimes
Feeling too tired, sleepy, and listless hampers efficient studying.	2.14	Sometimes
A dislike for certain courses and teachers disrupts school success.	2.10	Sometimes
Grand Mean	2.10	Sometimes

According to the study habits inventory table, the action of "pronouncing the words to myself as I read" obtained a mean score of 2.34, indicating a frequent occurrence, while the other habits were consistently described as occasional. Overall, the grand mean revealed a mean score of 2.10 which is verbally described as sometimes.

Table 5 Significant Difference of Level of Academic Stress, Level of Adjustment Styles, and Study Habits According to Sex

Sex	Mean	t	df	p
LEVEL OF ACADEMIC STRESS	Male	2.322	404	.021*
	Female			
LEVEL OF ADJUSTMENT STYLE	Male	.661	404	.509 ^{ns}
	Female			
LEVEL OF STUDY HABITS	Male	1.123	404	.262 ^{ns}
	Female			

The table presented the results of an Analysis of Variance test to examine potential significant differences in the levels of academic stress, adjustment styles, and study habits based on participants' gender. According to the findings, the academic stress level showed a t value of 2.322 with a corresponding p value of .021, which is below the 0.05 significance level. Conversely, the adjustment styles level yielded a t value of .661 with a corresponding p value of .509, exceeding the 0.05 significance level. Similarly, the study habits level obtained a t value of 1.123 with a

corresponding p value of .262, also not falling below the 0.05 significance level.

Considering the p values, it is evident that only the level of academic stress shows statistical significance, with a value less than 0.05. This outcome suggests a notable difference in academic stress levels among student nurses when categorized by gender. Conversely, the levels of adjustment styles and study habits, when grouped by gender, do not exhibit significant differences, as their p values are not less than 0.05.

Table 6 Significant Difference of Level of Academic Stress, Level of Adjustment Styles, and Study Habits According to Age

Age	Mean	F	Sig.
LEVEL OF ACADEMIC STRESS	18-20	18.112	.000*
	21-23		
	Total		
LEVEL OF ADJUSTMENT STYLE	18-20	5.089	.025*
	21-23		
	Total		
LEVEL OF STUDY HABITS	18-20	23.392	.000*
	21-23		
	Total		

The table displayed the results of an analysis of variance test, aiming to ascertain any significant differences in the levels of academic stress, adjustment styles, and study habits when participants were grouped according to their age. Based on the findings, level of academic stress obtained a f value of 18.112 with corresponding statistical significance of .000, level of adjustment styles obtained f value of 5.089 with corresponding statistical significance of .025, level of study habits obtained f value of 23.392 with corresponding statistical value of .000.

Considering their respective p values, all of which are below the 0.05 level of significance, the findings suggest a significant difference in the levels of academic stress, adjustment styles, and study habits among student nurses when categorized by their age. In other words, there is a measurable difference found based on age. Hence, the null hypothesis was rejected.

Table 7 Significant Difference of Level of Academic Stress, Level of Adjustment Styles, and Study Habits According to Religion

Religion	Mean	F	Sig.
LEVEL OF ACADEMIC STRESS	Roman Catholic	13.944	.000*
	Iglesia Ni Cristo		
	United Methodist Church		
	Born Again		
	Total		
LEVEL OF ADJUSTMENT STYLE	Roman Catholic	8.124	.000*
	Iglesia Ni Cristo		
	United Methodist Church		
	Born Again		
	Total		
LEVEL OF STUDY HABITS	Roman Catholic	13.506	.000*
	Iglesia Ni Cristo		
	United Methodist Church		
	Born Again		
	Total		

The table presented the results of an analysis of variance test, aiming to identify any significant differences in the levels of academic stress, adjustment styles, and study habits when participants were categorized based on their religious affiliation. Based on the findings, level of academic stress obtained a f value of 13.944 with corresponding statistical significance of .000, level of

adjustment styles obtained f value of 8.124 with corresponding statistical significance of .000, level of study habits obtained f value of 13.506 with corresponding statistical value of .000.

Considering the p values, all of which fall below the 0.05 level of significance, the findings suggest a notable difference in the levels of academic stress, adjustment styles, and study habits among student nurses when

classified based on their religious affiliation. In other words, there is a measurable difference found when based on their religion. Hence, the null hypothesis was rejected.

Table 8 Significant Difference of Level of Academic Stress, Level of Adjustment Styles, and Study Habits According to Family Monthly Income

Family Monthly Income		Mean	F	Sig
LEVEL OF ACADEMIC STRESS	Below 10,957	3.0867	.640	.590 ^{ns}
	10,958-21,914	2.9890		
	21,915-43,828	3.0495		
	43, 829-76,669	3.1131		
	Total	3.0347		
LEVEL OF ADJUSTMENT STYLE	Below 10,957	3.4604	1.816	.144 ^{ns}
	10,958-21,914	3.3411		
	21,915-43,828	3.3965		
	43, 829-76,669	3.5250		
	Total	3.3940		
LEVEL OF STUDY HABITS	Below 10,957	2.1232	1.244	.293 ^{ns}
	10,958-21,914	2.1114		
	21,915-43,828	2.0567		
	43, 829-76,669	2.0900		
	Total	2.1016		

The table presented the results of an analysis of variance test to investigate whether there are significant differences in the levels of academic stress, adjustment styles, and study habits among participants when grouped according to their family monthly income. Based on the findings, level of academic stress obtained a f value of .640 with corresponding statistical significance of .590, level of adjustment styles obtained f value of 1.816 with corresponding statistical significance of .0144, level of study

habits obtained f value of 11.344 with corresponding statistical value of .293.

Considering their individual p values, all of which are not less than the 0.05 level of significance, the outcome suggests that there is no significant difference in the levels of academic stress, adjustment styles, and study habits among student nurses when categorized based on their family monthly income. Consequently, the null hypothesis was accepted.

Table 9 Significant Relationship between Academic Stress and Study Habits

Significant Relationship between Academic Stress and Study Habits	Level of Study Habits
LEVEL OF ACADEMIC STRESS	Pearson Correlation
	Sig. (2-tailed)
	N
**. Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).	

The Table indicating the Chi-Square Test revealed a significant relationship between academic stress and adjustment styles. The obtained chi-square value was 0.259 with a corresponding statistical significance of 0.000. This implies a notable association between the levels of academic

stress and adjustment styles among nursing students, as indicated by Fuentes (2019). Fuentes primarily investigates whether parenting approaches are linked to improved outcomes in students' adjustment, despite consistent empirical evidence suggesting no significant variations.

Table 10 Significant Relationship between Study Habits and Adjustment Style

Significant Relationship between Study Habits and Adjustment Style	Level of Adjustment Style
LEVEL OF STUDY HABITS	Pearson Correlation
	Sig. (2-tailed)
	N
**. Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).	

The Table, featuring the Chi-Square Test, revealed a significant relationship between study habits and adjustment styles. The obtained chi-square value was 0.274, with a corresponding statistical significance of 0.000. This indicates a noteworthy association between the levels of study habits and adjustment styles among nursing students, as demonstrated by the Learning Style Inventory measuring dimensions like extrovert/introvert, sensate/intuitive, feeling/thinking, and judging/perceiving, along with the Study Habits Inventory measuring study habits (Harrison, 2015).

Table 11 Significant Relationship between Academic Stress and Adjustment Styles

Significant Relationship between Academic Stress and Adjustment Style	Level of Adjustment Style
LEVEL OF ACADEMIC STRESS	Pearson Correlation
	Sig. (2-tailed)
	N
**. Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).	

The Chi-Square Test presented in the table demonstrated a significant relationship between academic stress and study habits. The obtained chi-square value was 0.301, with a corresponding statistical significance of 0. This indicates a notable association between the levels of academic stress and study habits among nursing students, as highlighted by Fatima (2021). Fatima emphasizes the importance of students reducing academic stress and improving study skills, as these two factors play a crucial role in their academic performance.

IV. CONCLUSION

➤ Upon Reviewing the Provided Findings, the Following Conclusions were Derived:

- The results indicated that a significant portion of the participating students were 18-21 years old and majority of them were female. The majority of the participants reported a monthly family income ranging from 10,958 to 21,914, and most of them identified as Roman Catholic.
- The result showed that the level of academic stress was verbally described as moderate stress, with an overall mean score of (3.03).
- The findings indicated that the level of adjustment styles was verbally described as sometimes, with an overall mean score of (3.39).
- The findings revealed that the level of study habits was verbally characterized as sometimes, with an overall mean score of (2.10).
- The findings demonstrated a notable disparity in academic stress levels based on participants' gender, with no significant distinctions observed in adjustment styles and study habits concerning gender. Additionally, significant differences were identified in academic stress, adjustment styles, and study habits based on participants' age and religion. Conversely, no significant variations were noted in academic stress, adjustment styles, and study habits when participants were categorized according to their family monthly income.
- The findings revealed a significant correlation between the level of academic stress and study habits, as well as between the level of study habits and adjustment styles, and a significant relationship between academic stress and adjustment styles.

RECOMMENDATIONS

➤ Upon Completion of our Conducted Research, the Subsequent Recommendations were Derived.

- This suggests that future interventions and support systems should consider the specific needs and challenges faced by female students in this age group. Most of the respondents belonged to the Roman Catholic religion, indicating that cultural and religious considerations should be considered when designing interventions.
- The Researchers suggest that this highlights the importance of implementing strategies to mitigate stress and promote mental well-being among students. Given the significant difference in academic stress levels based on sex, tailored interventions targeting specific stressors experienced by male and female students may be beneficial.
- This indicates that they faced challenges in adapting to their academic environment. Addressing adjustment difficulties should be a priority, as effective adjustment styles can positively impact academic performance and overall well-being.
- The result of their study habits as "sometimes," suggesting that there is room for improvement in this area. Interventions focused on promoting effective study habits should be implemented to enhance academic performance and productivity.
- The Researchers come up with an intervention that considers these factors can better support students with different age groups and religious backgrounds. Family monthly income did not exhibit a notable variation in the levels of academic stress, adjustment styles, or study habits. However, it is still important to provide equal opportunities and support regardless of income levels.
- This implies that improving study habits and adjustment styles can potentially reduce academic stress levels. Interventions targeting these interconnected factors holistically can contribute to better academic performance and overall well-being.

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